

ANALYSIS AND FORECAST OF CHANGE OF FUEL EFFICIENCY INDICATOR OF PASSENGER AIRPLANES

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ABSTRACT:

The paper analyzes the current and long-term goals of ACARE, set out in SRIA, Flightpath 2050 and aimed at fuel consumption reduction. It is shown that one of the research task goals in PARE project to achieve ACARE goals is to evaluate methods for improving the fuel efficiency of an aircraft based on the implementation of modern concepts for creating a passenger airplane and its propulsion engine. The technical and economic characteristics of long-haul and regional aircraft are analyzed based on the determination of fuel efficiency of aircraft with different engine types for the period from 1958 to 2020. The effect of passengers number, flight range, type and thrust of engine on the change in fuel efficiency indicator of an aircraft is shown. Based on the information provided, fuel efficiency is forecasted to improve in the period 2020–2030 by less than 1% and no significant improvement in fuel efficiency indicator is expected.

INTRODUCTION

The active use of air transport for the mass transportation of passengers and cargos contributes to the increase in global greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Depending on future trends in the development of aviation and applied technologies, this share can grow even more. In the long view it is observed an increase in air passenger traffic, which will lead to greater fuel consumption, at the same time the emission of harmful substances into the atmosphere will increase [2, 3]. The global aviation community is widely discussing climate change mitigation on the planet [4]. The main area of discussion is the introduction of revolutionary technologies for minimal environmental impact and the expected success from the use of various types of aviation fuel [5, 6].

Improving the capacity of air transport is currently one of the most important aviation issues that will

help to reduce emissions, including CO₂. In this case, it is important to know about the prospects for the development of energy efficiency or fuel efficiency of aircraft, including new schemes, architectures and technologies [7]. The European aviation community is concerned about new global challenges in terms of its competitiveness, leading position, productivity, sustainability, and contribution to reducing emissions into the environment [8]. Maintaining global leadership and competitiveness in the aviation sphere is a priority mission for the European aviation industry over the coming decades.

In the European Union, the Advisory Council for Aeronautics Research in Europe (ACARE) [9] plays a key role in a long-term research strategy aimed at reducing the environmental impact of aviation, increasing the competitiveness and sustainability of the aviation industry. One of the main aims of ACARE is to initiate cooperation between concerned parties aimed at achieving the goals of Flightpath 2050 [10]. Currently, on the initiative of the PARE project partners [11], the researches are conducted to analyze and evaluate the fulfillment of all the goals of Flightpath 2050, to determine the level of progress, to reveal gaps and barriers for each of these goals and to develop recommendations for their addressing. One of the project research aims is to evaluate methods for increasing the fuel efficiency of a passenger aircraft based on the integration of its subsystems and new layout schemes.

ANALYSIS OF THE FUEL EFFICIENCY IMPROVEMENT PROBLEM

The integrated European transport system is based on general rules and standards, innovative business models, customer-oriented and uninterrupted transportation processes. The mobilization of all intellectual potential, material and human resources of various organizations of the Member States of the European Union is vital for the development of the future of the entire Europe [12, 13]. The aviation priority as industry advanced technological sector is crucial for

maintaining Europe's competitiveness in the global market, as the development of aviation often leads to the spread of applications in other sectors. Scientific and innovative achievements should be stimulated at the right time. Therefore, ACARE has developed a Strategic Research and Innovation Program (SRIA) for the EU to address the challenging long-term goals stipulated in its overall strategy, Flightpath 2050. The SRIA [10] defines specific tasks to achieve these ambitious goals.

To achieve these goals, a roadmap has been developed that includes 5 (five) global tasks [10]. Task No. 3 is Environmental protection and energy supply. This task solution should be carried out based on the future air vehicles design with the development of evolutionary steps. The key technological elements of the aircraft are:

- *airframe* (levels: weight reduction to reduce fuel consumption; resistance reduction to lower fuel consumption; noise reduction; efficient production (competitiveness); technological capabilities; operation);
- *power plant* (levels: increasing thermodynamic and propulsion efficiency; reducing environmental impact due to lightweight materials and structures; increasing the service life and reliability of components, increasing wing time, maintainability and time between overhauls; reducing emissions from combustion - NO_x, CO, UHC and particulate matters; reduction of aircraft noise associated with a power plant; improvement of ecological footprint due to environmentally friendly processes; use of effective technological means);
- *integration at the aircraft level* (sublevels: aircraft configuration, system and structural integration, integration of the power plant with an airframe, innovative power plants with low noise in the airframe, industrial integrated system, aircraft certification).

Other key areas are:

- the development of revolutionary technologies for low environmental impact and minimal fuel consumption;
- the development of innovative air vehicle configurations that minimize environmental impact and energy consumption;
- development of the concept of a new air vehicle and transport system that support innovative minimum environmental impacts, including minimum fuel consumption.

An analysis of the main subtasks of Task No. 3 of SRIA [10] shows that increasing the fuel efficiency of an aircraft depends not only on the perfection of the power plant, but also on the aerodynamic characteristics of the airframe.

CURRENT STATUS OF RESEARCH AND PROSPECTIVE DEVELOPMENTS

The world's aviation companies are intensively developing new architectures for integrated power plants that will have high fuel efficiency, minimal environmental impact and rational energy consumption [14, 15].

Today, the main traditional layout of the aircraft with the fuselage and engines under the wing is so well developed that its further improvement is associated with growing difficulties. Meanwhile, significant reserves to improve the aerodynamic perfection of the aircraft are laid in the integration and new airframe layouts. In addition, the friction drag, which is the result of air viscosity, remains an almost untouched field for scientists to study. As known, the flow energy is lost due to the presence of a boundary layer on the surface of the body as a result of the force interaction of a solid body (in this case, airframe) and air flow. With a laminar flow, friction losses are fewer, and with a turbulent flow, they are higher.

However, aircraft next generation will completely exhaust the reserve of improving the existing layout and it will be practically impossible to obtain significant results [16]. The revolutionary way of developing new aircraft is associated with deep integration, in which the apparent separation of the airframe and engine disappears. New design and layout schemes will significantly reduce engine fuel consumption.

The International Air Transport Association (IATA) deals with industry partners around the world to reduce fuel consumption or develop alternative fuels [17, 18]. Earlier it was adopted an ambitious goal, an average increase in fuel efficiency by 1.5% per year (since 2009 to 2020) [19].

A comprehensive cost estimate for short-term (up to 2024) and medium-term (up to 2034) technologies for increasing fuel efficiency for commercial aircraft in the United States is presented in the work [20]. Researches were conducted for three types of aircraft of different manufacturing companies: E190AR (RJ), A320-200 (SA) and B777-200 (STA), which are the most popular in operation [21-23]. Figure 1 presents a comparison of aircraft with cost-effective technologies, which provide high fuel efficiency at present, and the current market demand for new aircraft with high fuel efficiency. This research shows that fuel consumption in new aircraft designs can be reduced by about 25% in 2024 and by 40% in 2034 compared to modern aircraft.

Figure 1. Trends in fuel combustion for new aircraft to start operation (since 1980 to 2040)

This will become real through the introduction of new cost-effective technologies that provide net savings for operators over a seven-year period. The introduction of effective technologies with long-term trends in increasing fuel efficiency in new designs will more than double the expected reduction in fuel consumption by 2034 and up to 2.2% per year for the coming decades (Fig. 1). The ICAO has also set ambitious goals for the coming years to improve fuel efficiency [5, 8, 24]. These goals are based on technological progress, optimized maintenance of equipment, rational air traffic and infrastructure, sustainable use of biofuels and economic means. The ICAO Forecasting Commission analyzed various factors that will affect fuel consumption between 2010 and 2050. There is shown a forecast based on the total increase in fuel consumption per passenger-kilometer (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Fuel consumption forecast

Since air traffic is growing at a faster pace than improvements in aircraft design (multiplier 3.1 on the graph), total fuel consumption for this period (2010–2050) will double.

Improving engine performance, and as a result, increasing fuel efficiency, of the next generation is based on a number of new developments [25, 26]:

- highly efficient gas generator architecture along with new technologies (Fig. 3);
- lightweight carbon titanium fan system;
- multi-stage turbine gear system.

Figure 3. Efficiency trends for promising Rolls-Royce engines

Work [26] describes key technologies and engine architectures that lead to lower fuel consumption for large civil aircraft (Fig. 3). There is shown a new line of Rolls-Royce projects, as well as a demonstration of advanced technology. The development programs for the promising Ultrafan engine are supported by a comprehensive set of demonstration programs that cover the entire period of the engine's creation (Fig. 4). Rolls-Royce is researching the power plant workflow to improve fuel economy (Fig. 5). This is the main goal of the demonstration programs of engines of two- and three-shaft architecture (Advance3, UltraFan).

Figure 4. Ultrafan technology demonstrator creation program for next-generation engines (Rolls-Royce, Clean Sky)

Over the past two decades, European scientific and technical programs have been actively developing to improve various systems and engine components [26], to create new technologies for further improving the fuel efficiency of power plants (Fig. 6).

Figure 5. Specific fuel consumption as a function of driving and thermal efficiency

Figure 6. Technology programs of the European Union

The review articles [27, 28] describe possible improvements in fuel efficiency for different aircraft when introducing the concept of the engine demonstrator of the ENOVAL project. In the 7th FP7 framework program, three large projects, LEMCOTEC, EBREAK, and ENOVAL, were funded to research new technologies aimed at increasing the overall pressure ratio (OPR) and the bypass ratio (BPR) of aircraft engines [29, 30]. In the ENOVAL project, engines were studied for three classes of aircraft: small and medium (180 passengers / range of 6,500 nm), large (280 passengers / range of 11,000 nm) and very large aircraft (410 passengers / range of 10,000 nm). The project result is to improve the fuel efficiency

of the power plant and the aircraft, and thereby, meet the requirements of ACARE-2020 to reduce fuel consumption (Fig. 7). The indicated characteristics of aircraft affect the fuel efficiency indicator, which will be shown later in the research work.

Figure 7. Results of a comparative assessment of the fuel consumption of the ENOVAL program

Nonetheless, until 2035 there is still a 4–5% gap that needs to be taken into account in future European technology projects. However, SRIA goals can only be achieved using innovative technologies that can simultaneously increase thermal and motive efficiency [14].

Despite all the technologies that are included in the base airframe and power plant of 2050, the addition of radical technology is not enough to achieve ACARE 2050 goals on fuel efficiency [31]. The research results suggest that it is necessary to go beyond the traditional tube-wing design and use a higher degree of integration between the airframe and the radical engine in order to get closer to the set goals.

New aircraft configurations include a significant improvement in the aerodynamic data of the aircraft, reducing the weight of the aircraft, developing radically new engine architectures, developing configurations with a distributed power plant (Fig. 8).

Currently, with renewed vigor, interest is being shown in the creation of an “open rotor” engine. Such architecture will make it possible to reduce the fuel consumption of the power plant by 15-20% compared to other engine architectures. As part of the European DREAM project [32], Rolls-Royce, Snecma, together with CAI and other companies, conducted research on the demonstrator of the “open rotor” engine. During testing in a wind tunnel, impressive results were obtained that attest good prospects for this engine [31, 33].

Figure 8. Comparison of aircraft configurations by 2050 as for the degree of fuel consumption reduction

One of the methods to improve fuel efficiency is the use of Open Rotor technologies with new blades (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Boxprop blades with vortex tip and plug

Open rotor engines consist of one or two rows of screws located either in front or behind the power plant. For subsonic flights, these engines have more advantages in terms of propulsion (traction) efficiency (Fig. 10).

The works [34–36] list the key technologies of “Open Rotor” engines. It also shows the latest technology growth results made by Safran Aircraft Engines, with emphasis on the full-blown SAGE2 demonstrator, which was designed, configured and launched as part of the Clean Sky program. The results of the demonstrator with TRL5 in terms of integration and controllability of the configuration are presented.

Figure 10. Comparison of the efficiency of engines of various designs by flight Mach number

In addition to existing new generation aircraft, aviation can also count on the development of other innovative projects. Recently, Airbus, Rolls-Royce, and Siemens have chosen the development of a hybrid electric aircraft capable of carrying 50 to 100 passengers [37]. Boeing has launched a startup to develop a regional hybrid electric aircraft that will accommodate 10 to 30 passengers with a range of up to 1000 miles [37].

METHOD OF RESEARCH OF FUEL EFFICIENCY

Based on the data processing of the authors of works [38, 39], the presented research work presents the results of passenger aircraft fuel efficiency numerical analysis. To confirm the validity of the approach and the correct assessment of prospects, retrospective analysis includes aircraft of old models from 1950s. All the presented dependences are obtained by calculation. For analysis, aircraft with a cabin of class 2 and 3 (with a maximum number of passengers on board) were taken.

The first indicator of passenger aircraft operation is fuel efficiency, which is the ratio of the total amount of spent fuel in flight to the passengers carried on this route [40]. This indicator has a dimension – g/pass. • km, and is recorded:

$$k_1 = \frac{G_{fuel}}{n_{pass}V}$$

where G_{fuel} is hourly fuel consumption, kg/h;
 n_{pass} is number of passengers, pass. ;
 V is cruising speed, km/h.

The second indicator of fuel efficiency is expressed in (l/pass. • km):

$$k_2 = \frac{Q_{fuel}}{n_{pass}L}$$

where Q_{fuel} is fuel volume, l;
 n_{pass} is number of passengers, pass. ;
 L is flight range, km.

Using these indicators, it is possible to comprehensively evaluate a passenger aircraft of any design, with different types of engines (turbojet, turbofan, propfan) and any number of passengers on board. At their core, they reflect the perfection of an airframe and its power plant.

The work presents the results of calculating the fuel efficiency only by the k_1 criterion for passenger aircraft of the operation period from 1955 to 2020 (Fig. 11). The indicator k_2 has similar trends for each parameter. In each decade, 5 aircraft were chosen for calculation, and between 2000 and 2020, 18 aircraft were selected. The following are the results of researches of the aircraft that have been in operation only since 2000 and are of the greatest interest in terms of forecasting conditions.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

All data on the number of passengers, flight range and hourly fuel consumption are taken from sources [41, 42].

Fig. 11 shows that over the past 60 years, the criterion of fuel efficiency is constantly decreasing and the tendency to decrease is still preserved. If we take the data of the first Comet aircraft for 100%, then today the specific fuel consumption has decreased by almost 78%. In the first 30 years, criterion k_1 improved by 60-70%. The reason for the decrease in intensity in the 70s is the output of second-generation aircraft with an increased degree of bypass and a degree of

increase in pressure in the compressor. After this, significant changes did not occur. Over the past 10 years, the criterion has been reduced only by 1.2%.

Fig. 12-15 show the dependence of this criterion on the overall pressure ratio (OPR) increase in the compressor, engine thrust, bypass ratio (BPR), and the flight range of the aircraft.

Figure 11. Change in fuel efficiency criterion k_1 by years depending on OPR

Figure 12. Change in k_1 from the OPR increase in the compressor for different aircraft

Figure 13. Change k_1 from engine thrust

Figure 14. Change k_1 from the bypass ratio (BPR)

Fig. 15 shows the change in fuel efficiency of fuel k_1 depending on the purpose of the aircraft. The best values of this criterion have aircrafts with lower engine thrust and shorter flight range, the average value k_1 is less than $\approx 20\%$.

For a single aircraft, an increase in the number of passengers will lead to a decrease in the fuel efficiency indicator k_1 . Aircraft with fewer passengers on board have the best values of fuel efficiency indicator k_1 (Fig. 15).

As known, the main characteristics of the engine that affect fuel efficiency are the OPR in the compressor and the BPR. This is confirmed by the data shown in Fig. 12 and Fig. 14. It can be seen from the figures that an increase in BPR and OPR led to an improvement k_1 , but over the past 20 years this decrease is already insignificant - $<5\%$.

An analysis of the structural and layout schemes of aircraft shows that there is a separation of the indicator k_1 in geometric parameters. The value

k_1 increases in aircraft with a larger wing area and a large fuselage diameter.

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CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis of the researched aircraft characteristics and their development trends, a forecast is developed for the change in the fuel efficiency indicator, shown in Fig. 17. An optimistic forecast is expected as a result of the introduction of technological innovations in the airframe and the use of new engine design schemes with full integration of the layout of the subsystems. Such implementations should be launched in 2030.

Figure 17. The prospect of changing the indicator k_1 until 2050

A pessimistic forecast is based on the lack of improvements in fuel efficiency due to various circumstances, such as crises in the world or aviation, the reluctance of global manufacturers to change the existing aviation system due to huge financial investments, technical difficulties in introducing new components or products, etc. However, today it is already known that until 2030 a significant improvement in the fuel efficiency indicator k_1 is not expected.

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